

Use case fact-sheet

Actors

List all actors involved in the Use Case and the Geographic Information-related processes they are involved in, then put a “x” in correspondence to the relevant cells.

Who (actor) ²	What (Action) ¹					
	Data acquisition/creation	Data analysis/processing/validation	Data publication	Extraction of information from published data	Data maintenance	xxx
Decision makers				x		
Officers/technicians			x		x	
Researchers		x		x		
General Public				x		
xxx						

Table 1: Overview of the actors involved in the Use Case

Use Case (UC) main info	
Identifier	ZGZ-EI
Name	Emissions Inventory
Description	Preparation of a biennial emissions inventory, enabling the measurement of the effectiveness of mitigation measures. Two types of inventories targeted at decision makers and citizens, which encompass different sectors and a specific set of pollutants with a spatial resolution of 100x100 metres and an annual temporal resolution.
Primary User	Decision makers, citizens, technicians
Goal	To illustrate to the public how pollutant emissions are distributed across Zaragoza, identify priorities and critical points within the urban area, and inform decisions to mitigate them.
Owner	Oficina Técnica Transparencia y Gobierno Abierto, Oficina de Medio Ambiente, Acción Climática y Salud Pública
Status	Under development
Policy context	

¹ Add new processes or rename the existing ones or split the ones currently merged as you may find more appropriate

² Add new actors or rename the existing ones

<p>Challenges & Priorities</p>	<p>Together with the stable trend of rising temperatures, the municipal territory faces the problem of air quality. The quality of air is further influenced by the reduction in the balance between precipitation and evaporation. Overall, Zaragoza aims to reduce the emission levels of greenhouse gas such as CO₂ and other atmospheric pollutants, improve the air quality in the city and avoid health risks to its population.</p>
<p>Strategy/Plan/Regulation</p>	<p><u>Strategy for Climate Change, Air Quality and Health (ECAZ 3.0)</u>, is the first major policy instrument designed to coordinate climate mitigation actions. The main objectives of the strategy include the reduction of CO₂ emissions by 40%; the reduction of domestic waste that reaches the dump areas by 50%; and the reduction of the emissions of NO₂ by 60% in comparison to the levels of 2005. To achieve these objectives, 40 measures were planned in 4 different action areas, including urban planning, urban mobility, industry, and public services.</p> <p>In 2024, ECAZ 3.0 was further strengthened by the Climate City Contract, and its associated Climate Action Plan as part of EU Mission ‘100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030’. Together, these cross-cutting initiatives aim to reduce GHG emissions by 80% by 2030. The mitigation measures drawn up in these strategies rely on the emissions inventory updated biennially, which helps identify sectors with the greatest decarbonisation potential, including transport, buildings and heating, energy sources and waste management.</p> <p><u>Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan 2030 (SECAP/PACES 2030)</u> developed in 2022. PACES 2030 established the GHG inventory of 2005 as the baseline for Zaragoza, which is updated every 2 years. The mitigation action plan is composed of 23 measures. The use case specifically supports several PACES mitigation actions, i.e. 20, 21, 22 and 23, which among other things aim to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Encourage citizens co-responsibility and participation in the implementation of the Plan; ● Communicating the impact and results of actions; ● Promote climate-friendly lifestyles that improve air quality in the local community; ● Foster collective action and develop procedures and tools to monitor the realisation of the Plan. <p>Zaragoza <u>Climate Change Adaptation Plan 2030 (#PACCZ 2030)</u>. PACCZ 2030 is the second iteration of the PACES 2030 in terms of adaptation, as it presents an update of the Risk and Vulnerabilities Assessment and includes an adaptation action plan composed of 9 areas. Key measures include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Action Area 1 «Human Health», Measure 1.5 <p>This measure aims to establish a system for monitoring air quality (including meteorologic information, and pollen levels) to alert the public prior to situations of increased or extreme levels of contamination.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Action Area 5 «Territorial & urban planning, building & energy», Measure 5</i> <i>This measure aims to create an easily accessible geo-referenced cartographic system on the municipal website of urban elements: climate shelters, shaded areas, drinking fountains and ornamental water sources. This system can rely on the functionalities of the Open Government GeoPortal to create collaborative maps of the different urban areas affected by climate change. Moreover, the goal is to establish a system of adaptation indicators to track the benefits of PACCZ. This includes implementing infrastructure for monitoring climate and environmental indicators transversally throughout the territory, defining activities for data collection across different sectors included in the PACCZ and making periodic reports.</i> ● <i>Action Area 7 «Mobility and transportation», Measure 7.2</i> <i>The goals of this action area augment the actions around the attainments of Low Emission Zones. Notably, it proposes the development of a quantification methodology specific for Low Emission Zones (LEZ) which allows the deployment of actions at neighbourhood/district level. In the same context, it suggests the initiation of campaigns to measure the levels of exposure to atmospheric pollutants and their evolution.</i> ● <i>Action Area 8 «Education and society», Measure 8.2 and 8.3</i> <i>Both measures aim to strengthen community engagement, including citizens, by providing relevant, updated, and verified information on adaptation to climate change on the municipality website.</i> <p>Zaragoza <u>Urban Agenda 2030</u> and its Action Plan adopted in 2022, identifies and proposes the articulation of a series of actions in planning that integrates financing, governance, citizen participation and exchange and dissemination in relation to urban phenomena. The Agenda comprises 10 strategic objectives and a roadmap to guide the development of policies and specific actions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Strategic Objective 3 «Prevent and diminish the impact of climate change and improve resilience», Specific Objective 3.2 & 3.06</i> <i>These two objectives regard the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and air quality improvement. To reach them, the Action Plan entails six different actions, three of them dedicated to the development of ECAZ. To improve air quality by updating the extant system for obtaining more detailed information, both on contaminants not considered until now, and on greater spatial precision of the prediction. The new PRECOZ 2.0 will have a higher resolution for dispersion models of pollutants. This will allow predictions at district/neighbourhood levels, keeping the same temporal prediction.</i>
Local Green Deal / City contract(s)	<p>Climate City Contract with the Climate Action Plan is part of Zaragoza’s commitment to EU Mission ‘100 Climate Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030’. Alongside other strategies and action plans, these cross-cutting initiatives aim to reduce GHG emissions by 80% by 2030.</p>

European Green Deal Policy Area	Achieving climate neutrality (net-zero pollution) by reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 as foreseen by EU Climate Law. Reach the interim objective of a net 55% emission reduction by 2030, foreseen by the EU 'Fit for 55' package.
Precondition	
<p>List the pre-requisites (availability of input data, tools, etc.):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Input data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Consumptions datasets from the following sectors: agriculture- livestock, industry, mobility, residential, institutional, waste tertiary sector ● Tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tools to process the data in csv (OpenRefine) ○ Semantic Web Technologies (Protege, Chowkl, GraphDB, etc) ○ API Zaragoza to obtain data ○ Visualization services (Leaflet) 	
Postcondition	
DRI (Decision Ready Information)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Final Aggregated emissions by sector and year by cells (csv): https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a6f6005f-6ac7-4673-9e15-77758dedc562 ● Final Aggregated emissions by sector and year by cells (shapefiles): Data to be visualized in the visualization service https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/e4dd1b7f-e4d1-4f47-b05e-562b1ffd379e ● District level final aggregated emissions by sector and year (csv) (DRI): https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/298eb8e8-72c1-43bd-b144-aa7118ecd704 ● Final Aggregated emissions by sector and year by districts (shapefile): Data to be visualized in the visualization service https://usage.geocat.live/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/eac98d99-4576-4fac-8f74-4102b1d5363c
Use of DRI	- Decisions related to reducing emissions produced by by means of transportation, focusing on cars' emissions
Use case processing steps	
https://drive.google.com/file/d/1L84Zu45pZqcf77aZm0wRXhhS2yBeXgB_/view?usp=sharing	
DOI to processing steps BPMN	
https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15166538	

